

Kinetic and Mechanistic Study of Nitrite by Bromate and Ruthenium(III) Catalysed Iodate

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Kinetic studies of the oxidation of nitrite by bromate at $\text{pH} \approx 3$ and Ru^{III} catalysed iodate at 0.01 M $[\text{HClO}_4]$ have been studied. The reactions are acid catalysed. Ionic strength effects and effect of added salts are found to be marginal. The rate laws for the bromate oxidation and Ru^{III} catalysed iodate reaction have been discussed.

THE present study is concerned with the oxidation of nitrite by bromate and Ru^{II} catalysed iodate. As there is no perceptible reaction with iodate under the experimental conditions employed, a transition metal ion Ru^{III} has been chosen as a catalyst. Interestingly the reaction is facile in the presence of Ru^{III} . Hence, a detailed kinetic study is attempted.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade. 70% BDH (AR) HClO_4 , RuCl_3 (Johnson and Mathey) was standardised by the method of Horiuchi *et al.*¹ and the desired concentration was maintained by dilution. Sodium nitrite (E. Merck) solutions were standardised cerimetrically². The kinetics of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted bromate or iodate idometrically towards conventional starch end point. In all the kinetic runs 5 ml aliquots were added to 50 ml ice-cold water containing sulphamic acid. Sulphamic acid decomposed nitrite, which otherwise interferes with the iodometric determinations³.

Potassium hydrogen phthalate and hydrochloric acid were used to maintain the pH which was measured by using a Systronic 335 Digital pH meter. The rate constants are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ error.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ on the reaction rate: The order with respect to bromate is unity (as evidenced from the linearity of $\log$ titre vs time plots up to at least three half lives). Moreover, the pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the slopes of these plots are almost constant over a six fold variation in the initial concentration of bromate (Table 1).

Effect of varying $[\text{IO}_3^-]$ on the reaction rate: The order with respect to oxidant is proved to be zero as the plots of percentage vs time are fairly linear up to at least two half lives. Zero order rate constants are computed from slopes (x/t) of such

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$, $[\text{NaClO}_4]$, $[\text{NO}_2^-]$ AND $[\text{Cl}^-]$ ON THE RATE

$[\text{NO}_2^-] = 0.005 \text{ M}$		$\text{pH} = 2.9$		$\text{Temp.} = 35^\circ$
$[\text{BrO}_3^-] \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$[\text{NaClO}_4] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{NO}_2^-] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{Cl}^-] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
2.5	5.0	—	—	1.84
5.0	—	—	—	1.92
8.8	—	—	—	1.88
14.8	—	—	—	1.85
5.0	10.0	—	—	1.92
—	15.0	—	—	1.95
5.0	5.0	5.0	—	2.08
—	—	10.0	—	2.09
5.0	5.0	—	1.0	1.77

linear plots. Moreover, k_1 values computed for various initial concentration of IO_3^- are almost identical, confirming the zero order dependence with respect to the oxidant (Table 2) in the concentration range studied. Such zero order dependence has been observed in various reactions catalysed by transition metal ions.

Effect of varying $[\text{NO}_2^-]$ on the reaction rate: The rate of the reaction increases on increasing $[\text{NO}_2^-]$ (Table 3). The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{NO}_2^-]$ is a straight line at a fixed pH 3 for bromate oxidation. For iodate oxidation this slope is found to be unity.

Effect of added salts and ionic strength on the rate: The bromate oxidation reaction has been followed in the presence of salts like, KCl , NaNO_3 and NaClO_4 . The salts are found to have almost no influence on the rate. The iodate oxidation has been studied at various concentrations of NaClO_4 and no change in rate has been observed (Table 1).

Effect of varying solvent mixture on the rate: Results in Table 4 reveal that the bromate oxidation rate increases on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium, whereas the iodate oxidation rate (Table 5) is insensitive to the changes in dielectric constant.

Effect of changing pH on the ratio: The bromate oxidation reaction is immeasurably fast below pH 2

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [Oxidant], [Substrate], [Acid], [Catalyst] AND [NaClO₄] AT TEMPERATURE 35°

Substrate [NO ₂ ⁻] × 10 ³ M	Oxidant [IO ₃ ⁻] × 10 ⁴ M	Acid [HClO ₄] × 10 ³ M	Catalyst [Ru ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ M	[NaClO ₄] × 10 ³ M	K _o × 10 ⁻³ mol l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
5.0	2.6	1.0	1.528	5.0	1.48
5.0	5.2	1.0	1.528	5.0	1.40
5.0	11.3	1.0	1.528	5.0	1.48
5.0	20.9	1.0	1.528	5.0	1.88
2.5	5.0	1.0	1.528	5.0	0.91
10.0	5.0	1.0	1.528	5.0	8.2
20.0	5.0	1.0	1.528	5.0	5.6
5.0	5.0	1.0	0.882	5.0	0.85
5.0	5.0	1.0	0.704	5.0	0.73
5.0	5.0	1.0	8.056	5.0	2.86
5.0	5.0	0.5	1.528	5.0	0.79
5.0	5.0	2.0	1.528	5.0	2.54
5.0	5.0	4.0	1.528	5.0	3.94
5.0	5.0	1.0	1.528	2.5	1.57
5.0	5.0	1.0	1.828	10.0	1.6
5.0	5.0	1.0	1.528	15.0	1.6

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [NO₂⁻] ON THE REACTION RATE

[BrO₃⁻]=5 × 10⁻⁴ M, [NaClO₄]=0.05 M, Temp.=35°
Aqueous medium pH=3

[NO ₂ ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
2.8	0.70
5.0	1.23
10.0	2.30
15.0	3.84

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SOLVENTS ON THE RATE

[NO₂⁻]=0.005 M, [BrO₃⁻]=0.0005 M, [NaClO₄]=0.05 M, Temp.=35°

Solvent	% (v/v)	pH	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
Dimethyl sulphoxide	20	3.53	0.96
Acetonitrile	20	3.80	1.09
Acetic acid and 0.1 M sodium acetate	25	2.68	6.40
Acetic acid and 0.02 M sodium acetate	15	2.36	10.86

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF PERCENTAGE OF HOAc, ON THE REACTION RATE

[IO₃⁻]=0.0005 M, [NO₂⁻]=0.005 M, [HClO₄]=0.01 M, [Ru^{III}]=1.528 × 10⁻⁴ M, [NaClO₄]=0.05 M, Temp.=35°

HOAc %	k _o × 10 ⁻³ mol l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
0	1.42
5	1.52
10	1.48
20	1.62
40	1.65

and imperceptibly slow beyond pH 4. For all kinetic runs, therefore, the pH of the solution was varied around 3 by keeping the concentration of potassium hydrogen phthalate constant and changing the concentration of hydrochloric acid in the

buffer in the reaction mixture (Table 6). At this pH the decomposition of nitrite is minimum and almost negligible. The log k values are found to vary linearly with pH. Increase in the concentration of HClO₄ increases the rate of iodate oxidation (Table 2). The plot of log k_o vs log [H⁺] is linear with positive slope of less than unity indicating fractional dependence on acid.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF CHANGING pH ON THE RATE

[BrO₃⁻]=5 × 10⁻⁴ M, [NaClO₄]=0.05 M, [NO₂⁻]=5 × 10⁻³ M, Aqueous medium, Temp.=35°

pH	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
2.48	6.40
2.55	4.10
2.87	1.92
3.0	1.28
3.05	1.15
3.30	0.58
3.55	0.25
3.74	0.18

Effect of varying temperature on the rate: The reactions are carried out at different temperatures (35, 40, 45 and 50) with a view to compute the Arrhenius activation parameters. The plot of log (rate constant) vs 1/T is found to be linear. The values of ΔE[‡], ΔH[‡], log₁₀A and ΔS[‡] are 67.0 kJ mol⁻¹, 64.4 kJ mol⁻¹, 7.8 and -103.0 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively for bromate oxidation and 35.9 kJ mol⁻¹, 33.3 kJ mol⁻¹, 0.76 and -239.1 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively for iodate oxidation.

Effect of varying [Ru^{III}] on the iodate oxidation reaction rate: The oxidation potential of BrO₃⁻ is 1.44 V and that of IO₃⁻ is 1.08 V. The low potential of iodate system is probably the reason why it is ineffective to oxidise HNO₂. However, in presence of catalytic amount of a transition metal ion, Ru^{III}, the reaction becomes facile. Increasing the concentration of Ru^{III} increases the reaction rate (Table 2). The plot of log k_o vs log [Ru^{III}] is

Dividing equation (1) throughout by $[H^+]^2$, we get,

$$\frac{\text{Observed rate}}{[H^+]^2} = K_s[NO_2^-] \left\{ \frac{k_3}{[H^+]} + k_2 k_5 \right\} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) requires that a plot of observed rate/ $[H^+]^2$ vs $1/[H^+]$ should be a straight line with an intercept on the rate axis which is in fact observed. This provides support in favour of the mechanism proposed and rate law derived. The small intercept obtained in the above plot is indicative of a very small contribution from the second term involving $HBrO_2$ in the absence of which a plot passing through the origin would have been obtained.

Mechanism of iodate reaction: It is well known that the transition metal ion easily form complexes due to the presence of vacant 'd' orbitals. In view of the fact that iodate in the present experiment does not participate in or prior to the rate determining step, complexation between Ru^{III} and HNO_2 in an equilibrium step is proposed. A very high negative entropy value is in agreement with the formation of an ordered transition state. The complex then breaks down in a slow step with an internal electron transfer to form Ru^{II} . The existence of Ru^{II} complexes are well known^{2,3,12}. A rapid isomerisation of the nitro group from O-bound nitrito $Ru^{III}-ONO$ to N-bound $Ru^{III}-NO_2$ takes place after which electron transfer occurs. A two electron oxidation of the nitro to nitrate occurs and the reduction is delocalised over two sites, i.e. metal and nitro group¹⁴.

In view of the stability of various Ru^{II} complexes the above scheme is valid. The Ru^{II} thus formed is oxidised back to Ru^{III} in a fast step. NO_2 radical

as reaction intermediate has been reported¹⁵ earlier in the nitrous acid oxidation by Mn^{III} .

Rate law: Applying steady state treatment for the formation and decomposition of the complex a rate expression (equation 3) can be written based on this mechanism.

$$v = \frac{k_2 k_3 K_s [NO_2^-] [H^+] [Ru^{III}]}{(1 + K_s [H^+]) (k_{-2} + k_3)} \quad (3)$$

This rate law explains all the observed facts.

So, a plot of $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ should be a straight line with an intercept on the inverse rate axis which is in fact observed. This proves the validity of the mechanism and the corresponding rate law derived.

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References

1. Y. HORIUCHI and O. ICHIVYO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 72, 50694.
2. H. H. WILLARD and P. YOUNG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 55, 8260.
3. S. KAPOOR and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1019.
4. N. S. BAYLISS and B. W. WATTS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1956, 9, 319.
5. T. A. TURKEY and O. A. WRIGHT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2415.
6. G. STEDMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2948, 2949.
7. K. JONES, "The Chemistry of Nitrogen, Pergamon Texts in Inorganic Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1978, Vol. IIb, pp. 372-78.
8. C. A. BUNTON and G. STEDMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3466.
9. J. O. EDWARDS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 50, 455.
10. J. P. BIRE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, 17, 604.
11. R. DAVIES, B. KIPLING and A. G. SYKES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 7250.
12. J. C. BAILAR, M. J. BMELEUS, R. NYHOLM and A. F. T. DICKERSON, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Pergamon, London, 1978, Vol. III, p. 1198.
13. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTI and N. C. SAHU, *Kinet. Katal.*, 1981, 22, 627.
14. F. R. KERNE, D. J. SALMON, J. L. WALSH, H. D. ABRUNA and T. J. MEYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 1896.
15. E. C. THOMPSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 7315.